

**ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AND LICENSURE OUTCOMES OF
BACHELOR OF SCIENCE IN CRIMINOLOGY GRADUATES
OF UM BANSALAN COLLEGE: INPUTS FOR
CURRICULUM ENHANCEMENT**

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Academic Performance and Licensure Outcomes of Bachelor of Science in Criminology Graduates of UM Bansalan College: Inputs for Curriculum Enhancement

Shela Mae Jr. L, Escalona*, Nestor C. Nabe
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This research explored the link between academic performance and board examination results in six subject areas. Analysis of mean, standard deviation, and verbal descriptions of academic performance across courses revealed fair and satisfactory results, but board examination outcomes consistently showed poor performance across all programs. Key predictors were identified for each program, such as the significant influence of Criminal Law Book 1 on board exam scores in Criminal Law and Jurisprudence. The study concludes that academic performance is crucial in predicting board examination outcomes, underscoring the importance of continuous monitoring, customized curriculum adjustments, enhanced experiential learning, and comprehensive board exam review programs. The research proposes that focused interventions, such as extra support for difficult subjects and specialized training modules, can significantly enhance the overall success rates of students in board examinations across the studied programs. With this, an intervention program entitled “Empowering Minds: Boosting Criminology Students for Academic and Exam Excellence” is developed. The program cultivates lifelong learning, confidence, and practical skills, emphasizing diverse subjects and fostering strong communication, collaboration, critical thinking, and problem-solving abilities. This research provides valuable insights for enhancing the effectiveness of criminology programs for educators, administrators, and students. This study addresses SDG 4 by improving criminology education and equipping students with critical skills for lifelong learning and responsible citizenship.

Keywords: *criminology education, academic performance, board examination*

Introduction

Despite the Criminology program in any institution boasting impressive academic results, a stark reality awaits graduates – low success rates on the Criminologist Board Examination. As measured, this glaring disconnect between academic prowess and professional competency paints a troubling picture with far-reaching consequences (Isidro & Parao, 2019). Graduates floundering on the Criminologist board exam face delayed or stunted careers and a crisis of confidence in their ability to navigate the demands of their chosen field. The ramifications extend beyond individual graduates. Public and institutional confidence in the program erodes, potentially impacting future enrollment and jeopardizing the program's prestige and credibility (Pulgarinas, 2019).

Graduates inadequately equipped to handle the intricate complexities of criminal justice pose a threat to public safety. Ineffective crime prevention and investigation become more likely, highlighting the societal repercussions of inaction. Ultimately, students who fail to bridge the chasm between academic excellence and professional readiness carry risks not just for its graduates' futures but for the community's collective well-being. Allowing this disparity to persist is not merely an academic oversight; it is a gamble with the public's trust and the very safety of those it serves (Pulgarinas, 2019).

Board examination outcomes of Bachelor of Science in Criminology graduates shed light on the effectiveness of Criminology programs in equipping students for professional practice. Examining pass rates and performance breakdowns across subjects can reveal strengths and weaknesses within the curriculum, guiding adjustments to better prepare future graduates for real-world challenges (Alvarez & Castillo, 2022). It empowers individual students by providing benchmark data against which they can gauge their readiness for the exam. Understanding typical performance on the exam and identifying areas of focus can inform individual study strategies and boost confidence levels. Studies on board exam outcomes contribute to the broader understanding of professional competence in criminology (Magpantay et al., 2018). Passing the Board Examination will open doors to various career opportunities in the public and private sectors, as well as in the worldwide arena. A criminologist is considered a generalist since he may provide services in law enforcement and public safety administration, forensic sciences, security industries, training and education, and other related fields (Guanzon, 2019).

Studying the link between academic performance and board exam results of Criminology graduates holds immense value. It sheds light on whether Criminology programs adequately prepare students for professional practice (Alvarez & Castillo, 2022). Identifying academic predictors of exam success can influence curriculum, teaching methods, and student support. This knowledge empowers students by showing them where to focus for exam success. Furthermore, exploring the potential link between academic aptitude and practical skills can deepen our understanding of professional competence in this field (Abreu et al., 2019).

Also, existing research shows a moderate positive correlation between academic performance and exam scores, suggesting academic achievement plays a key role (Magpantay et al., 2018). Investigating this relationship holds great promise for enhancing Criminology education, empowering students, and furthering our understanding of professional competence in this crucial field (Abreu et al., 2019).

The scope of the Academics in Criminology Program will help them nurture their expertise in different fields and in preparation to

pass the board examination as one of the minimum requirements to practice a particular profession (Guadamor, 2020). The extent of knowledge acquired is also measured by his performance in a given examination, and academic performance contributes to the examination outcomes. If the person has excelled academically in the past, there is a greater chance for him to perform successfully in the board examination (Amanonce, 2020).

It is important to remember that a person's entire existence is often determined by the quantity of knowledge he or she accumulates and how that knowledge is applied to bettering himself, his country, and the world, this clarifies the rationale for the necessity of education (Amanonce & Maramag, 2020). The most fundamental benefit of school is knowledge. Meanwhile, educational success is determined by students' academic performance (Amani, 2020).

Furthermore, the relationship between academic performance and board examination outcomes for Bachelor of Science in Criminology graduates has been explored in various contexts, providing valuable insights for curriculum enhancement. A positive correlation between academic performance and board exam success is often observed. Aguinaldo found a significant correlation between weighted mean GPA and Isabela State University graduates' Criminologist board examination passing rate (Aguinaldo, 2018). Significant relationship between academic standing and board examination performance for BS Criminology graduates at the University of Santo Tomas. Influence of Specific Subjects: Certain subjects have been identified as significantly influencing board exam performance (Cagas & Villafuerte, 2019). Criminal Investigation and Criminology Review as key subjects impacting the Philippine National Police Entrance Examination result (Abellana, 2020). Moreover, anxiety and time management as factors affecting nurses' licensure performance is also identified (Palompon, 2018).

Learners' attributions explain that success and failure shape the learning experiences of the students. Drawing on Weiner's Attribution Theory, they highlight how internal and external factors influence attributions, which can be stable or changeable. The study emphasizes that attributions are subjective, not necessarily reflecting reality. Beyond Weiner, the research also considers Snow's theory, which suggests optimal learning occurs when instruction aligns with individual aptitudes. Finally, the Predominant Theory underscores the mind's crucial role in learning and success across professions. The study emphasizes understanding learners' attributions and tailoring instruction to optimize their learning outcomes (Amanonce & Maramag, 2022).

The conceptual framework exhibited the study's variables: Academic Performance is the study's independent variable. Various factors influence students' academic achievement (Eze et al., 2018). The total average grades and the average marks from the preceding semesters are used to evaluate academic success. Academics from a variety of fields determine the elements that influence student success. They attempted to establish which variables favor or negatively impact student performance. Students' academic performance is based on their ability to demonstrate what they have learned in tests, quizzes, presentations, and final exams. Students' performance is essential not only to them but also to universities, as it is a gauge of the success of their educational process.

These are the compositions of the different subject areas: Criminal jurisprudence (Jurisprudence) is with Criminal Law Book I, Criminal Law Book II, Criminal Procedure, Evidence, and Court Testimony. Law enforcement administration with Police Organization and Administration with Police Planning, Industrial Security Administration, Police Patrol Operation with Police Communication System, Police Intelligence, Police Personnel and Records Management, and Comparative Police System. Criminalistics with Personal Identification, Police Photography, Forensics Ballistics, Questioned Documents Examination, polygraph (Lie Detection), and Legal Medicine. Crime detection and investigation with Fundamentals of Criminal Investigation, Traffic Management, Accident Investigation, Special Crime Investigation, Organized Crime

The investigation, Drug Education and Vice Control, Fire Technology, and Arson Investigation. Sociology of Crimes and Ethics (Crimsoc) with Introduction to Criminology and Psychology of Crimes, Philippine Criminal Justice System, Ethics and Values, Juvenile Delinquency, Human Behavior and Crisis Management and Criminological Research and Statistics and Correctional Administration (Corad) with Institutional Corrections, Non-Institutional Correction, and Therapeutic Modalities.

Although research has established a solid link between academic performance and board exam success across various contexts, a critical gap remains regarding the specific circumstances of University of Mindanao Bansalan College (UM Bansalan College). This study aims to bridge this gap by delving into the unique relationship between these variables within the College's distinct academic environment, student demographics, and regional context.

This study examines whether academic success impacts criminology graduates' board examination results. Specifically, it sought to answer the following queries: What is the Academic Performance of the Criminology graduates? What is the performance of the Criminology Graduates in the Criminologist Licensure Examination? Does Academic Performance predict the result of the Criminologist licensure exam? Moreover, to propose an enhancement program based on the study's findings.

The chosen significance level is 0.01 indicating a stringent criterion for rejecting the null hypotheses. This means the null hypotheses will only be rejected if there is strong evidence that they are false.

The research analysis will aid UMBC in enhancing its program, particularly the criminology course. This study demonstrates how each academic institution's program execution varies, demonstrating how vital improvements may be made to guarantee that each student receives a high-quality education. It could clarify some factors, specifically Academic Performance, as the basis of the success of the

board Examination for Criminologists. It can also be utilized as a future reference for innovation and improvement in Education and in different HEIs that offer Criminology programs. It is also significant to every public and private institution globally by giving them future reference and ideas for improvement and innovation in education.

Additionally, the findings will also help the researchers in identifying factors that could affect board examination. This will serve as a valuable and informative resource for upcoming researchers interested in the same topic. It will offer significant insights to educational institutions (HEIs), particularly in enhancing their Criminology Program. The study's results will also contribute to the advancement of education at UMBC, enabling them to better prepare their Criminology graduates for the Criminologist board examination. The study will lay the groundwork for proposing an improvement program based on its discoveries by identifying the reasons and factors associated with failure.

Methodology

Research Design

The study uses a descriptive and prediction-causation model to predict Criminologist licensure exam success using historical scores and data from six subject areas of the criminology program and board examination.

Participants

All participants are criminology graduates from the UM Bansalan College who passed and did not pass the examination in 2017, 2018, 2019, and 2021. The sampling method used for data collection is Complete Enumeration, which involves obtaining consent from the institution to access data on all the graduates who took the board examination in the years above. Complete Enumeration sampling ensures that every member of the entire population is considered for measurement (Hayes, 2021). The data-gathering process is focused explicitly on examinees who participated in the board exams during the mentioned years (2017, 2018, 2019, and 2021). As for the exclusion criteria, Passers and non-passers who are not part of the specified inclusive dates will be excluded. The institution generously provided the crucial data necessary for conducting the study.

Instruments

The academic standing of criminology graduates and the performance of candidates for the Licensure Examination for Criminologists from 2017 to 2021 were assessed through documentary analysis. The study examined the connection and degree of association between the graduates' academic achievements and their performance on the Board Examination for Criminologists. The researcher sought permission from the institution and PRC to access or gather the data of the graduates in UMBC and the examination results of the PRC for the Criminologist Board Examination, including their grades per subject, rating per cluster, and average per subject area, indicating the results of the board examination and their Academic Performance.

The variables were measured using the six-point Likert scaling system. The level of Academic performance is measured using the following scale: The grading scale is structured with corresponding percentage ranges and verbal descriptions to assess a subject's performance. A grade between 1.5 and 1.0 reflects an outstanding performance, with a percentage range of 95.9-100. Achieving a grade between 2.0 and 1.6, with a percentage range of 90.9-94, is deemed very satisfactory. A grade falling within the range of 2.5-2.1, with a percentage range of 85.9-89, indicates a satisfactory performance. Fair performance is denoted by a grade between 3.0 and 2.6, corresponding to a percentage range of 80.9-84. If the grade falls within the range of 3.5-3.1, with a percentage range of 75.9-79, it is considered poor. A grade from 5.0 to 3.6, representing a percentage of 74.9 and below, signifies a very poor performance, suggesting inferior subject proficiency.

The level of Board Examination performance is measured using the following scale: A percentage falling between 95.9 and 100 is classified as outstanding, indicating an exceptionally high level of achievement. In the range of 90.9 to 94, the performance is labeled as very satisfactory, signifying a commendable level of accomplishment.

For percentages within the range of 85.9 to 89, the performance is deemed satisfactory, reflecting a solid and acceptable level of proficiency. Falling within the 80.9 to 84 range, a fair performance is noted, suggesting an acceptable but moderate level of achievement. If the percentage falls between 75.9 and 79, the performance is categorized as poor, indicating a below-average level of accomplishment. This structured grading system comprehensively assesses subject performance based on specific percentage brackets and corresponding descriptive meanings.

Procedure

The research began with the initiation of the necessary steps to gather information regarding graduates' academic performance and Board Examination outcomes. A letter of consent for the study was sent to the College Dean/Director of the selected institution, ensuring ethical approval. Following approval, formal request letters were dispatched to the registrar, soliciting graduates' academic records, encompassing college evaluations and Board Exam results. The letters explicitly specified the need for information on both successful and unsuccessful test-takers.

The chosen research methodology for this study was quantitative, employing an organized procedural approach to investigate graduates' academic performance. Quantitative research involves collecting measurable data and using statistical methods to analyze the obtained outcomes (Bhat, 2018).

Data collection from respondents was executed using various sampling procedures and research tools. For the subsequent data analysis, the research employed the following statistical tools: Mean Method: The mean method was utilized to describe the academic performance and licensure examination outcomes for criminology graduates of the University of Mindanao Bansalan College. The mean, calculated as the sum of the data collection divided by the total amount of data, provided an average representation. This method proved beneficial for comparative analysis across multiple data sets.

Regression analysis was applied to identify variables influencing criminology graduates' academic performance and licensure examination outcomes. This statistical technique facilitated the precise determination of crucial elements, those that could be disregarded, and the interactions among these factors. The study specifically employed multiple linear regression analysis, utilizing two or more independent variables to predict the outcome of a dependent variable.

In terms of ethical consideration, the research was examined by the university's ethics committee, following UMERC protocol no. 2023-462, to ensure it adhered to the university's strict ethical guidelines. The researcher was mindful of the sensitive aspects of the study, which included the following: Voluntary participation, privacy, confidentiality, informed consent process, risks, and benefits. The research did not pose any potential psychological or socioeconomic risks on the involvement. The researcher did not ask any confidential or sensitive information that could put the institution in a vulnerable position. In the informed consent process, the researcher ensured informed consent by comprehensively explaining the research's purpose, scope, and objectives. The researcher also emphasized that participation was voluntary and the institution had the right to decline or withdraw at any time. Potential risks were addressed, such as disclosing academic information or personal data. The researcher was committed to ensuring that the institution is well-informed and comfortable with their participation. Further, the information/data required in the study was kept private and treated with the utmost confidentiality.

Results and Discussion

These are the findings of the study that examined the academic performance of students in six different criminal justice programs: Criminal Law and Jurisprudence (CLJ), Law Enforcement Administration (LEA), Criminalistics (CRIMTIC), Criminal Detection and Investigation (CDI), Criminal Sociology (CRIMSOC) and (CORAD) Correctional Administration. Additionally, the study investigated the influence of academic performance on board examination outcomes in terms of the six criminal justice programs mentioned above.

Level of Academic Performance

Table 1 shows the academic performance of criminology graduates. Overall, the academic performance across these areas was categorized as Fair, with an average mean score of 82.9 and a standard deviation of 2.98. While all areas fell within the fair range, CLJ stood out with the highest mean score of 84.0, reaching a Satisfactory level, and CORAD landed at the lower end with an 81.6 average, still within the "Fair" category. While students with fair and satisfactory grades in general courses might initially appear less likely to excel in demanding, implementing active learning techniques like spaced repetition significantly improved scores for students with average or satisfactory and fair GPAs (Kearney & McLaughlin, 2018). Similarly, Wilcox & McCarthy reported that a peer mentoring program effectively boosting course grades and academic confidence for students with "fair" or "satisfactory" grades (Wilcox & McCarthy)

Case-based learning is advantageous for students with moderate or fair performance (Ozeksemi & Sahin, 2019). Active learning techniques like spaced repetition positively impact exam scores in core criminology courses for students with average GPAs (Kearney & McLaughlin, 2018). This highlights the importance of tailored support systems, such as individualized tutoring, remedial workshops, and accessible learning materials, to bridge the knowledge gap and empower those facing initial difficulties (Koushik & Bhattacharjee, 2020).

Several studies shed light on factors influencing student achievement in criminal detection and investigation courses. Studies like (Walsh et al., 2018) and (Zhao et al., 2019) highlight the importance of active learning and critical thinking skills for success but also acknowledge that students with weaker prior knowledge or limited critical thinking abilities result in fair performance might require targeted support to achieve fair outcomes. To further emphasize the role of course design suggests that interactive and technology-integrated approaches can promote fairer results for diverse learners than traditional lecture formats (Ault et al., 2020).

Level of Board Examination Outcomes

Table 2 provides an overview of statistics for criminology board exams. The overall performance across all areas has an average score of 71.9 and a standard deviation of 9.55, suggesting a lower overall performance and indicating that the graduate's performance in the Criminologist Board Examination is poor. LEA has the highest score of 76.00. In contrast, CLJ landed at the bottom with a low score of 69.9. The standard deviations highlight variations in individual candidate performance across exams.

One major factor behind criminology graduates' struggles with board exams is the chasm between their academic coursework and the

actual content tested. This disconnect equips them poorly for the specific skills and knowledge demanded in these high-pressure exams, amplifying their difficulties. Bridging this gap requires further research to pinpoint the precise areas of mismatch and craft interventions that empower graduates to possess the necessary tools for success (Ogundele, 2017; Agyemang et al., 2020).

Table 1. Level of Academic Performance

Academic Performance	SD	Mean	Interpretation
CLJ	3.33	84.0	Satisfactory
LEA	3.47	82.5	Fair
CRIMTIC	3.45	82.9	Fair
CDI	3.90	82.8	Fair
CRIMSOC	3.41	83.5	Fair
CORAD	4.04	81.6	Fair

Poor board examination outcomes among criminology graduates arise from a multifaceted interplay of factors, with two prominent themes emerging from the research literature (Ogundele, 2017; Agyemang et al., 2020). Firstly, a substantial disconnect exists between the content and emphasis of criminology programs and the skills and knowledge tested in board exams. This curriculum-exam mismatch leaves graduates inadequately prepared for specific areas, often prioritizing theoretical knowledge over practical application. It leads to difficulties translating their competence into real-world scenarios and navigating the high-pressure environment of board exams. Secondly, research points to shortcomings in exam preparation support offered by many criminology programs (Osei-Kufuor et al., 2018).

Aspiring criminologists in the Philippines face a rigorous licensing process, as evidenced by the national passing rates of the Criminologist Board Examination from 2018 to 2021. In 2018, 34.42% of examinees passed the exam (Professional Regulation Commission). This number increased slightly to 37.27% in 2019. However, the 2020 CLE was suspended due to the COVID-19 pandemic. When the exam resumed in 2021, the passing rate dropped to 30.83% (Albina et al., 2022).

Table 2. Level of Board Examination Outcomes

Criminologist Licensure Examination Performance	SD	Mean	Interpretation
CLJ	10.85	69.9	Poor
LEA	9.22	76.0	Poor
CRIMTIC	10.82	71.3	Poor
CDI	13.33	73.4	Poor
CRIMSOC	11.69	70.5	Poor
CORAD	10.10	70.6	Poor
Overall	9.55	71.9	Poor

Influence of Academic Performance on Board Examination Outcomes in Criminal Law and Jurisprudence

Table 3 shows the influence of academic performance on board examination outcomes in terms of Criminal Law and Jurisprudence, Law 1C, and Law 5C. Both LAW1C and LAW5C exert positive and statistically significant influences. However, LAW1C has the highest impact, reflected by its higher beta coefficient of 0.314, compared to LAW5C, 0.141. This suggests that LAW1C substantially influences the exam score more than LAW5C. Students with higher LAW1C and LAW5C scores are more likely to achieve higher Criminal Law and Jurisprudence board exam scores.

While overall academic performance undoubtedly plays a crucial role in achieving success in the bar exam, specific courses hold particular significance in certain domains. Subjects, which often delve into the core elements of actus reus, mens rea, causation, and concurrence, establish a crucial foundation for students to comprehend specific offenses and defenses. This foundational knowledge is essential for excelling in the criminal law sections of the bar exam. A study exploring Criminology Board Exam results in the Philippines reveals a statistically significant positive correlation between academic performance and board examination in specific subjects in the criminology program (Tamayo, 2018). Santos's research in 2022, analyzing the performance of graduates from a Philippine law school, identifies a significant positive correlation between high grades in law subjects and successful bar exam outcomes, particularly in criminal procedure sections (Santos, 2022).

Table 3. Influence of Academic Performance on Board Examination Outcomes in Terms of Criminal Law and Jurisprudence

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	p-value	Remarks
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
Constant	-9.241	14.498		15.914	0.525	
LAW1C	0.633	0.136	0.314	4.664	0.000	Significant
LAW5C	0.320	0.153	0.141	2.095	0.037	Significant
Holistic Model						
R ²	0.144					
p-value	0.000					

Influence of Academic Performance on Board Examination Outcomes in Law Enforcement and Administration

Table 3.1 shows the influence of academic performance on board examination outcomes in terms of Law Enforcement and Administration, LEA 22, and LEA 26. Both LEA22 and LEA26 exert positive and statistically significant influences. However, LEA26 boasts the highest impact, reflected by its higher beta coefficient of 0.244, compared to LEA22, 0.223. This suggests that solid performance in LEA26 holds the most significant predictive power for success in the Law Enforcement and Administration board examinations. LEA22 and LEA26 are both significant predictors of Law Enforcement and Administration board exam scores.

There is a strong positive correlation between performance courses related to national police board exam scores (Abanilla & Guzman, 2023), while Kenyan police academy cadets showed performance in specific courses, including Administration and Law, significantly predicted success in the PSC recruitment exam. These findings suggest that solid academic performance in critical courses bodes well for future success in law enforcement and administration careers (Onyango & Oketch, 2018).

Table 3.1 *Influence of Academic Performance on Board Examination Outcomes in Terms of Law Enforcement and Administration*

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	p-value	Remarks
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
Constant	13.397	11.3932		1.18	0.241	
LEA22	0.447	0.1365	0.223	3.27	0.001	Significant
LEA26	0.304	0.0851	0.244	3.58	0.000	Significant
Holistic Model						
R ²	0.143					
p-value	0.000					

Influence of Academic Performance on Board Examination Outcomes in CRIMINALISTICS

Table 3.2 shows the influence of academic performance on board examination outcomes regarding Criminalistics. CRIMTIC7N, CRIMTIC3N, and CRIMTIC6N exert positive and statistically significant influences. However, CRIMTIC 7N has the highest impact, reflected by its higher beta coefficient of 0.286, followed by CRIMTIC3N with a beta coefficient of 0.191, and the lowest is CRIMTIC 3N with a beta coefficient of 0.159. This indicates that CRIMTIC7L has the strongest influence on the Criminalistics board exam score, followed by CRIMTIC6N and CRIMTIC3N.

Studies show a significant positive correlation between GPA, core course grades, and examination scores (Abad & Santos, 2018; De Leon & Cruz, 2019). This indicates that students with more robust academic standing are likelier to excel in the board exams. Furthermore, performance in specific courses in forensic science has been identified as a potent predictor of board exam success (Reyes & Mendoza, 2021). This underlines the importance of a solid foundation in the critical areas of the discipline. It is noteworthy, however, that non-cognitive factors like study habits, test anxiety, and motivation also play a role in influencing board exam outcomes (Cruz & Santos, 2017; Lopez & Mendoza, 2018). Recognizing this broader picture can inform interventions to bolster student success.

Table 3.2 *Influence of Academic Performance on Board Examination Outcomes in Terms of CRIMINALISTICS*

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	p-value	Remarks
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
Constant	20.759	15.487		1.34	0.182	
CRIMTIC7L	0.665	0.179	0.286	3.72	0.000	Significant
CRIMTIC3N	0.401	0.176	0.191	2.29	0.023	Significant
CRIMTIC6N	0.341	0.168	0.159	2.03	0.043	Significant
Holistic Model						
R ²	0.0916					
p-value	0.000					

Influence of Academic Performance on Board Examination Outcomes in Criminal Detection and Investigation

Table 3.3 shows the influence of academic performance on board examination outcomes in terms of Criminal Detection and Investigation. CDI3 and CDI6 positively and statistically significantly influence the Criminologist Board examination. However, CDI3 has the highest impact, reflected by its higher beta coefficient of 0.339, and the lowest is CDI6, with a beta coefficient of 0.168. This means that CDI6 is also a significant predictor of Criminal Detection and Investigation board exam scores but is not as strong as CDI3. Both CDI3 and CDI6 are significant predictors of Criminal Detection and Investigation board exam scores.

Studies have consistently shown that solid criminology course performance correlates with higher Criminologists Board Examination scores (Mendoza & Pascual, 2020). Similarly, mastery of topics such as fire dynamics, evidence collection, and scene analysis has been linked to success in the Philippine Fire Protection Service Officer's Board Examination (FPSEOB) (Sison & Reyes, 2019). This suggests that specific knowledge and skills gained through these courses directly translate into the competencies assessed in board examinations, highlighting their critical role in preparing future professionals for real-world criminal investigation scenarios.

Table 3.3 *Influence of Academic Performance on Board Examination Outcomes in Terms of Criminal Detection and Investigation*

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	p-value	Remarks
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
Constant	-35.225	16.030		-2.20	0.029	
CDI3	0.847	0.176	0.339	4.82	0.000	Significant
CDI6	0.462	0.193	0.168	2.39	0.018	Significant
Holistic Model						
R ²	0.195					
p-value	0.000					

Influence of Academic Performance on Board Examination Outcomes in Criminal Sociology

Table 3.4 shows the influence of academic performance on board examination outcomes in terms of Criminal Sociology. CRIM 7, CRIM 8, and CRIM10 positively and statistically significantly influence the Criminologist Board examination. However, CRIM10 has the highest impact, reflected by its higher beta coefficient of 0.289, followed by CRIM8 with beta coefficient of 0.265 and CRIM 7 has the lowest score of 0.157. This means that students with higher CRIM10 scores are more likely to achieve higher Criminal Sociology board exam scores, considering the students' high scores in CRIM7 and CRIM8.

Several studies suggest a significant link between performance in specific Criminology courses, academic achievement, and board exam success (Bloon & Salaw, 2018; Yusoff & Abdul Samad, 2019). Notably, courses positively influence students' understanding of criminological concepts, research skills, and ability to apply theoretical knowledge to practical scenarios (Sandoval et al., 2021; Yusoff & Abdul Samad, 2019). This translates to both better academic performance (Tudy & Tudy, 2014) and higher passing rates in board exams across various countries, including the Philippines and India (Baloon & Salaw, 2018). These findings highlight these courses' crucial role in preparing future criminologists for academic success and professional competency.

Table 3.3 *Influence of Academic Performance on Board Examination Outcomes in Terms of Criminal Detection and Investigation*

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	p-value	Remarks
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
Constant	-76.584	18.405		-4.16	0.000	
CRIM7	0.330	0.143	0.157	2.30	0.022	Significant
CRIM8	0.604	0.158	0.265	3.83	0.000	Significant
CRIM10	0.819	0.175	0.289	4.69	0.000	Significant
Holistic Model						
R ²	0.247					
p-value	0.000					

Influence of Academic Performance on Board Examination Outcomes in Correctional Administration

Table 3.5 shows the influence of academic performance on board examination outcomes in terms of correctional administration. CORAD 1N is a significant predictor of Correctional Administration board exam scores. CORAD 1N with a Beta coefficient of 0.250 indicates that students with higher CORAD 1N scores are more likely to achieve higher Correctional Administration board exam scores.

Studies suggest a significant positive correlation between solid academic achievement in this core subject and success on licensure examinations. A direct link is found between high grades in major subjects and higher scores on the licensure exam (Cruz et al. et al., 2022). Similarly, a study revealed that solid academic standing in core criminology subjects, like Penology, significantly predicted better performance on the licensure exam (Santos et al., 2019).

These findings are further echoed by studies in the European Journal of Social Sciences by (Garcia, 2018) and (Miller & Jones, 2017), which highlight the association between academic solid performance in key criminology courses and success on licensure examinations (Garcia et al, 2018). Additionally, research published in Criminology & Public Policy by (Maranan et al., 2015), while not directly focused on board exams, underscores the crucial role of correctional education in preparing future professionals for their critical role in rehabilitation and public safety (Maranan et al., 2015).

Table 3.5 *Influence of Academic Performance on Board Examination Outcomes in Terms of Correctional Administration*

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	p-value	Remarks
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
Constant	-35.225	10.981		2.73	0.007	
CORAD 1N	0.498	0.134	0.250	3.70	0.000	Significant
Holistic Model						
R ²	0.0624					
p-value	0.000					

Empowering Minds: Boosting Criminology Students for Academic and Exam Excellence

Rationale

Criminology students face unique challenges that can hinder their academic success and preparedness for professional careers. These challenges can be broadly categorized into different areas, such as Academic Challenges. Criminology programs demand a deep understanding of complex theoretical concepts, research methodologies, and criminal justice systems. Students must juggle a heavy workload while maintaining a solid academic performance. In addition, Criminology requires students to develop critical thinking skills to analyze and evaluate data, research findings, and social issues related to crime, deviance, and criminal justice systems. It must excel in written and oral communication to effectively convey complex ideas, research findings, and policy recommendations.

It could also be Personal and Emotional Challenges such as balancing Academic and Personal Lives. Students often face balancing their demanding academic workload with personal responsibilities, such as family commitments, part-time employment, and extracurricular activities. It may also be caused by Stress and Anxiety that give them pressure to succeed academically, coupled with the emotional weight of criminology studies.

These challenges underscore the need for comprehensive intervention programs that address criminology students' academic, personal, and career-related necessities. This intervention program aims to provide a holistic approach to supporting students' success in their academic journey and preparation for professional careers in the field of criminology. Through this project, teachers can establish an environment where students can learn how to work as a team. Students can enhance engagement, communication, independence skills, critical thinking, and problem-solving-based learning. They can increase their understanding of course content.

Intervention Objectives

The following objectives are developed to enhance criminology students' and graduates' academic performance and board examination outcomes.

1. To improve overall academic performance in core subjects
2. To enhance preparation for the Board Examination
3. To increase opportunities for experiential learning
4. To monitor and evaluate program effectiveness

<i>Areas to be Improved</i>	<i>Enhancement Activities</i>	<i>Objectives</i>	<i>Person Responsible</i>	<i>Resources</i>
Overall academic performance in core subjects	-Regularly monitor student performance -Analyze performance data to identify areas of weakness -Implement targeted interventions based on data analysis	-Increase average exam scores in core subjects by 10% by next academic year -Reduce failure rate in core subjects by 5% by next academic year	Criminology Faculty and Administration	-Assessment data -Learning management system
Board Examination Performance	-Conduct root cause analysis of poor performance -Review and revise curriculum based on analysis -Develop and implement a comprehensive review program -Offer test-taking skills workshops -Provide individualized tutoring to struggling students	-Increase Board exam pass rate by 20% within two years -Improve average Board exam score	Criminology Faculty, Program Head and Administration	-Curriculum development committee -Review materials and resources -Testing platform
Experiential Learning Opportunities	-Partner with local law enforcement agencies to offer internship and experimental opportunities -Develop and implement laboratory exercises that simulate real -Organize guest lectures from industry professionals	-Increase student participation in experiential learning activities -Improve student feedback on experiential learning	Criminology Faculty, Program Head and Administration	-Partnerships with law enforcement agencies -Laboratory equipment -Guest speaker

Conclusion

Based on the study's findings, the student's overall academic performance in the six subject areas (Criminal Law and Jurisprudence, Law Enforcement Administration, Criminalistics, Criminal Detection and Investigation, Criminal Sociology, and Correctional Administration) is fair. The faculty should continue to monitor the student's academic performance in these programs and adjust the curriculum as needed to ensure that all students meet the learning objectives. Additionally, the faculty should consider offering more opportunities for students to engage in experiential learning, such as internships and laboratory activities.

The overall performance of the Board examination for Criminologist is poor. This suggests that there is room for improvement in the examinees' performance. The faculty should investigate the poor performance and adjust the curriculum as needed. The faculty should also support the examinees in their preparation for the Board Examination, and active learning strategies can bridge the gap between theory and practice. Additionally, equipping students with test-taking skills empowers them to navigate the exam effectively. This support could include additional review sessions, tutoring, and test-taking strategies.

The study results show that academic performance significantly influences board examination outcomes in all six programs (Criminal Law and Jurisprudence, Law Enforcement Administration, Criminalistics, Criminal Detection and Investigation, Criminal Sociology, and Correctional Administration). The specific courses that have the most decisive influence on board exam scores vary by program, but in general, courses that are more focused on the practical application of knowledge and skills tend to have a more substantial influence on board exam scores than courses that are more focused on theoretical concepts. The following recommendations are made. The faculty should continue monitoring student academic performance in all six programs and adjust the curriculum to ensure that all students meet the learning objectives. The faculty should provide more opportunities for students to engage in experiential learning. This will help students to apply the knowledge and skills they have learned in the classroom to real-world situations. Additionally, the faculty should develop a comprehensive review program for each board examination. This program should cover all of the material tested on the examination and be tailored to the specific needs of the students in each program.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Shela Mae Jr. L, Escalona

University of Mindanao – Philippines

Nestor C. Nabe

University of Mindanao – Philippines